
Dynamic Monitoring of Wheat Cultivation Patterns in Henan Province Based on Center-of-Gravity Shift and Cross-Section Analysis

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Abstract: Addressing cropland “non-grainification,” this study integrates standard deviational ellipse, centroid shift, and profile analysis of high-resolution wheat maps (2015, 2019, 2024) to reveal spatiotemporal dynamics in Henan. Results show a stable centroid in Xuchang, nonlinear “northeast–then–southwest” migration reflecting east–west structural shifts, fixed peak zones with intensified core–plain clustering, and a net area increase of 477.60 km²—driven by Zhumadian but offset by declines in Zhoukou and Shangqiu—confirming an evolution logic of “stable total, reinforced core, adjusted periphery,” offering scientific support for optimized agricultural layout and differentiated cropland protection.

Keywords: wheat; Center of gravity shift; standard deviational ellipse.

1. Introduction

Grains form the foundation of the national economy; food security is crucial to social stability and holds significant practical importance for ensuring national security [1]. In recent decades, China’s food security has faced a series of challenges. On the one hand, since the launch of reform and opening-up, rapid urbanization and the swift development of transportation networks have led to a substantial reduction in China’s arable land area. On the other hand, in pursuit of higher profits, some regions have shifted from growing staple crops to cash crops, giving rise to a trend of “non-grain use”—where arable land is converted from food production to other purposes [2]. In recent years, the involvement of industrial and commercial capital in agriculture has become widespread, with an increasing influx of urban industrial and commercial capital into rural areas [3]. Some industrial and commercial entities have acquired large tracts of farmland through land transfers to cultivate non-grain crops. This phenomenon of farmland “de-grainification” not only leads to a series of soil degradation issues [4] but also poses a threat to food security [5]. China ranks fourth in the world in terms of arable land area; however, due to its large population, per capita arable land reserves are insufficient [6]. Coupled with the massive outflow of rural populations in recent years and the involvement of industrial and commercial capital in agriculture, phenomena such as “non-grain use, reduced grain cultivation, and land abandonment” have become widespread [7]. As the area of land devoted to crop cultivation decreases, grain supply continues to fall short of demand despite rapid advancements in agricultural technology.

In the face of these practical challenges, China has consistently prioritized food security as its top priority [8], continuously strengthening support for food production through various measures and policies, thereby providing a solid foundation for national economic and social development. To safeguard arable land for grain cultivation, in November 2020, the General Office of the State Council issued the “Opinions of the General Office of the State Council on Preventing the ‘Non-grain Use’ of Farmland and Stabilizing Grain Production,”

which proposed “resolutely making the assurance of national food security the primary task of work related to agriculture, rural areas, and farmers,” “resolutely preventing the trend of farmland being used for non-grain purposes,” and “implementing responsibilities for grain production” [9]. In addition, the state has formulated a series of policies, such as the arable land protection system, the construction of high-standard farmland, and the orderly guidance of industrial and commercial capital into rural areas, to safeguard food security through multiple channels.

Henan Province enjoys a strategic geographical location and, thanks to its favorable natural environment, has become a major grain-producing region in China. In recent years, however, due to factors such as labor migration, changes in the natural environment, and policy adjustments, the area under wheat cultivation has varied to varying degrees across cities in Henan Province. Therefore, monitoring the spatiotemporal evolution of wheat cultivation distribution in Henan Province can provide a scientific basis for formulating food security policies and adjusting the agricultural structure, and is of great significance for promoting the sustainable development of agricultural ecosystems.

2. Overview of the Study Area and Data Introduction

Overview of the Study Area

Henan Province is located in the central-eastern part of China, in the middle and lower reaches of the Yellow River. With a total area of approximately 167,000 km², the province features a terrain that slopes from west to east. The province’s topography is complex and diverse, encompassing mountains, hills, basins, plains, and water bodies. The province boasts a well-developed river system, spanning the four major river basins of the Yellow River, Hai River, Huai River, and Yangtze River. It features an advantageous distribution of water and soil resources, with an agricultural cropping system primarily based on a “wheat-rice” rotation. As a core national grain-producing region, Henan Province serves not only as a key base for ensuring national food security but also as a central area for the implementation of major strategies such as ecological conservation and high-quality development in the Yellow River Basin.

Figure 1: Map of the Study Area

Data Overview

Administrative Boundary Data

See Figure 1 for a map of the administrative divisions of Henan Province; the vector boundaries are sourced from the National Geographic Information Public Service Platform (<https://www.tianditu.gov.cn/>).

Wheat Data

The datasets on the spatial distribution of wheat cultivation for 2015, 2019, and 2024 used in this study were obtained from the National Ecological Science Data Center (<https://www.nesdc.org.cn/>), and the spatial distribution is shown in Figure 2. The dataset has an overall accuracy of 89.88% and is highly applicable. It was generated by Yuan Wenping's team [10] using Landsat series remote sensing imagery in combination with the time-weighted dynamic time warping (TWDTW) method.

Figure 2: Spatial Distribution of Wheat Cultivation

3. Method

Standard Deviation Ellipse

Directional analysis of spatial patterns can reveal the contours and dominant trends of geographic features, and is commonly used in fields such as population migration, economic spatial evolution, and crop cultivation mapping [11]. The standard deviational ellipse (SDE), on the other hand, can accurately characterize the centripetal force, dispersion, and azimuth of geographic feature distributions [12]. Therefore, this study introduces the standard deviational ellipse to quantitatively characterize the wheat cultivation patterns in Henan Province over the past decade, aiming to reveal the evolutionary characteristics of wheat's spatial distribution at the macro-scale. This method defines the attributes of spatial distribution through several geometric parameters: the geometric center of the ellipse represents the relative center of mass of wheat cultivation in geographic space; the boundary of the ellipse defines the thematic area of wheat cultivation, reflecting the spatial extent of core production zones; azimuth reflects the directional extension of wheat cultivation distribution influenced by natural factors such as topography; the major and minor axes of the ellipse represent the primary axis of spatial evolution and the direction of evolutionary constraints, respectively; and the flattening reflects the non-uniformity of spatial distribution. The mathematical expressions for the key indicators of the standard deviation ellipse are as follows:

$$SDE(x, y) = \left(\left(\frac{\sum_{t=1}^m (x_t - X)^2}{m} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}, \left(\frac{\sum_{t=1}^m (y_t - Y)^2}{m} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \right) \quad (1)$$

In the equation, (x_t, y_t) represents the spatial coordinates of the study subjects, (X, Y) denotes the average center of the points, and m is the total number of points; $SDE(x, y)$ represents the coordinates of the center point of the study subjects.

$$\begin{cases} \gamma_x = \sqrt{2} \left[\frac{\sum_{t=1}^m (x_t \cos \theta - y_t \sin \theta)^2}{m} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ \gamma_y = \sqrt{2} \left[\frac{\sum_{t=1}^m (x_t \sin \theta - y_t \cos \theta)^2}{m} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In the equation, γ_x and γ_y represent the standard deviations along the x -axis and y -axis, respectively.

This study utilized the Directional Distribution (Standard Deviation Ellipse) tool in ArcGIS 10.8's Spatial Statistics module (with the ellipse size parameter set to 1_STANDARD_DEVIATION) to quantitatively characterize the clustering patterns of wheat distribution from 2015 to 2024 across three dimensions: fluctuations in coverage extent, shifts in the dominant direction, and changes in the degree of shape flattening.

Center of Gravity Shift Method

The center of gravity indicator can reveal trends and trajectories in the expansion of cultivated land [13]. If the center of gravity exhibits a directional shift, this indicates that wheat cultivation is expanding into the region toward which it is shifting.

In recent years, driven by a combination of factors—including the optimized allocation of water resources, adjustments to agricultural policies, and economic incentives—the spatial distribution pattern of wheat cultivation in Henan Province has undergone changes. An in-depth analysis of the trends in the center of gravity not only helps identify the underlying patterns of spatiotemporal variations in regional productivity but also provides a solid theoretical foundation for the precise allocation of resources in Henan's wheat industry. Against this backdrop, this study selected wheat planting area data from 2015, 2019, and 2024 to systematically examine the spatiotemporal evolution of the region's wheat planting patterns from the perspective of shifts in the center of gravity.

According to the geographical center of gravity model, the formula for calculating the coordinates of the geometric center of the wheat planting area is as follows:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{X} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^m A_{nt} \times X_t}{\sum_{t=1}^m A_{nt}} \\ \dot{Y} = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^m A_{nt} \times Y_t}{\sum_{t=1}^m A_{nt}} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In the equation, t represents the specific year of wheat cultivation; X_t represents the longitude coordinate of the center of wheat cultivation in the n -th year; Y_t represents the latitude coordinate of the center of wheat cultivation in the n -th year; \dot{X} and \dot{Y} represent the latitude and longitude coordinates of the pixels within the study area, respectively; A_{nt} represents the wheat cultivation area of the t -th pixel in the n -th year (in this study, if the pixel is classified as wheat, then $A_{nt} = 1$; if the pixel is classified as non-wheat, then $A_{nt} = 0$); m is the total number of pixels in the study area.

Using the wheat cultivation center of gravity model and formula, calculate the coordinates of the wheat cultivation center of gravity in Henan Province for the years 2015, 2019, and 2024, along with the municipalities where the center of gravity is located, as well as the distance, direction, and speed of its movement. Then, connect the coordinates of the wheat cultivation center of gravity for these three periods to obtain the migration trajectory of the wheat cultivation center of gravity in Henan Province from 2015 to 2024.

Latitude-Longitude Profile Analysis Method

To reveal the spatial differentiation characteristics of wheat cultivation along the longitudinal and latitudinal axes, this study introduced a cross-sectional analysis method. By extracting area time series in both longitudinal and latitudinal directions [14][15], the study accurately identified the spatiotemporal evolution trajectories of wheat distribution areas in Henan Province and analyzed the evolutionary logic of wheat cultivation patterns at the micro-scale, thereby providing a scientific basis for optimizing agricultural spatial layout. The specific procedure is as follows: The study area was divided into a regular grid with 1,000-meter grid cells. By aggregating the wheat cultivation areas within each grid cell, gradient statistics were performed on the wheat grid data for the three time periods of 2015, 2019, and 2024, and distribution curves of cultivation density along latitude and longitude were generated. The calculation formula is as follows:

$$\begin{cases} S_{Y,t} = \sum_{N_t \in Y,t} N_t \\ S_{X,t} = \sum_{N_t \in X,t} N_t \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Here, $S_{Y,t}$ and $S_{X,t}$ represent the total number of wheat pixels within the Y_t -th latitude grid and the X_t -th longitude grid, respectively; N_t denotes the number of classified pixels within the t -th grid; for wheat pixels, N is set to 1, otherwise it is set to 0.

4. Results & Discussion

Analysis of the Spatial Distribution Patterns of Wheat Cultivation

The major and minor axes of the standard deviation ellipse characterize the degree of dispersion and the extent of coverage of wheat cultivation patterns along the primary directions. Combining Table 1 with Figure 3 reveals that from 2015 to 2019, the lengths of both axes of the ellipse significantly shortened, indicating increased spatial concentration of wheat cultivation and reduced fragmentation at the periphery; however, by 2024, the values of both axes rebounded and approached 2015 levels, suggesting that cultivation areas expanded outward once again, leading to increased spatial dispersion. This fluctuating “contraction–expansion” trajectory is the result of the combined effects of agricultural policy orientation, rigid water resource constraints, and the dynamics of “non-grain use” and reclamation of farmland during the urbanization process.

Figure 3: (a) Standard deviation of the elliptical distribution. (b) Center of Gravity Trajectory.

Changes in azimuth reflect the rotational characteristics of the primary axis of wheat cultivation. In 2015, the azimuth was 29.92° , shifting counterclockwise to 24.01° by 2019, indicating that the primary cultivation axis was converging toward a north-south orientation; by 2024, this value had rebounded to 29.51° , re-establishing an east-west extension trend. These directional changes in the azimuth reflect the constraining and guiding effects of topography and infrastructure on the evolution of wheat cultivation.

The ellipticity index remained generally stable from 2015 to 2024, at 0.2661, 0.2712, and 0.2683, respectively. This indicates that although the trajectory and coverage of wheat cultivation have shifted, the morphological structure of its spatial distribution has not undergone fundamental restructuring, and its anisotropic characteristics have persisted.

Table 1: Standard Deviation Ellipse Indicator

Year	X coordinates	Y coordinates	X-axis/m	Y-axis/m	Rotation angle	Flattening
2015	800543.19	3765027.59	122177.03	166476.26	29.92°	0.2661
2019	802161.11	3765004.59	112470.82	154318.10	24.01°	0.2712
2024	798289.85	3764184.83	119666.92	163552.01	29.51°	0.2683

Analysis of the Spatio-Temporal Evolution of Wheat Cultivation Patterns

Based on changes in the latitude and longitude coordinates of the spatial center of gravity (see Table 2), the center of wheat cultivation during the study period was located between 114°13'52" and 114°16'27" E, and 33°58'19" and 33°58'44" N. The center of gravity was consistently situated within Xuchang City, exhibiting a nonlinear migration pattern characterized by an initial shift eastward followed by a retreat to the southwest.

Table 2: Location of the center of wheat cultivation

Year	Longitude	Latitude	City of focus
2015	114°15'23"E	33°58'42"N	Xuchang
2019	114°16'27"E	33°58'44"N	Xuchang
2024	114°13'52"E	33°58'19"N	Xuchang

Between 2015 and 2019, the center of wheat cultivation shifted 4,191.25 meters to the northeast; this spatial pattern evolution resulted from the combined effects of expansion in the eastern production areas and contraction in the western production areas. However, by 2024, the trajectory of the center of gravity reversed, exhibiting a pattern of "southward displacement and westward return." This revealed significant adjustments in the cropping structure along the southern periphery of the study area, which in turn drove the overall center of gravity to drift toward the southwest. The inset in Figure 3b clearly illustrates this "V"-shaped, zigzagging migration trajectory, reflecting the complex spatial reorganization of wheat distribution patterns over the decade.

Table 3: Shift in the Focus of Wheat Cultivation

Period	Migration distance(m)	Migration speed(m/year)	Migration direction
2015-2019	4191.25	1047.81	Northeast
2019-2024	4192.25	1048.06	Southwest
2015-2024	4193.41	465.93	Southwest

Analysis of Spatial and Temporal Variations in Latitude and Longitude

As shown in Figure 4a, the spatial distribution of wheat cultivation is primarily concentrated between 32°14'N and 36°24'N; however, due to the combined constraints of the subtropical climate transition zone and topography, wheat cultivation areas virtually disappear south of 32°14'N. Two clusters are observed along the latitudinal profile: the first peak is located near 33°04'N, with a cultivation area exceeding 150 km²; the second major peak is distributed between 33°54'N and 34°30'N, with an area exceeding 200 km². Temporal comparisons reveal that the profiles for 2015, 2019, and 2024 are highly consistent in shape, indicating that the macro-latitudinal pattern of wheat cultivation exhibits strong stability, though micro-level variations still exist. In 2024, the curve exhibited increased fluctuations north of 35°N, with some peak points showing a slight northward shift or an increase in peak values, indicating a slight expansion of the northern cultivation boundary or an increase in planting density in northern regions.

The longitudinal profile shows that the wheat cultivation area in the segment between 110°18'E and 112°26'E has long remained at a low level (approximately 50 km²), which is attributed to the barrier effect of the mountainous and hilly terrain in the west; however, as the curve moves eastward from 113°30'E into the heart of the Huang-Huai-Hai Plain, the planting area surges, reaching a regional maximum at 114°30'E (exceeding 300 km²), thereby establishing the eastern Henan region as the core of the province's wheat production. Temporal comparisons reveal that the intensity of the main peak shows an increasing trend across the three periods. In 2024, the curve values in the 114°E–115°E peak segment were higher than in previous years, indicating a strengthening of the agglomeration effect in the core production area. Meanwhile, the area in the eastern

peripheral region declined sharply to low values, reflecting the rigid constraints imposed on the cultivation range by provincial administrative boundaries and topographic transition zones.

Figure 4: (a) Latitude profile curve. (b) Longitude profile curve.

Distribution of Wheat Cultivation Patterns

The spatial distribution patterns of wheat cultivation significantly influence the distribution of agricultural productivity and regional sustainable development. Their dynamic evolution reflects the crop's adaptation to the environment, as well as the complex interrelationships among socioeconomic factors, farmland conservation policies, and ecosystems. Consequently, this study focuses on the 18 prefecture-level cities in Henan Province. Based on statistical data on wheat planting areas from 2015 to 2024, it systematically analyzes the evolutionary characteristics and driving mechanisms of the province's wheat spatial distribution over the past decade. The aim is to reveal the underlying logic of changes in planting patterns from multiple dimensions, thereby providing a scientific basis for ensuring regional food security and optimizing the agricultural spatial structure. During the period from 2015 to 2024, wheat planting area in Henan Province exhibited a trend of first increasing and then decreasing. Between 2015 and 2019, the province's wheat planting area increased by 842.89 km², reflecting the effectiveness of agricultural capital investment and the development of high-standard farmland. However, since 2019, influenced by multiple factors such as policy adjustments and changes in crop structure, the planting area began to decline, dropping to 56846.69 km² by 2024 a decrease of 365.30 km² from the previous peak. Overall, the wheat planting area increased by 477.60 km² during this period, fully demonstrating Henan's crucial role as a major national grain-producing region in ensuring food security.

Table 4: Statistics on Wheat Planting Area, Unit: km²

Year	2015	2019	2024	2015~2019	2019~2024	2015~2024
Puyang	2456.96	2464.17	2192.78	7.21	-271.39	-264.18
Anyang	2750.28	2844.01	2793.34	93.74	-50.67	43.07
Zhoukou	8384.27	8751.85	8140.15	367.58	-611.70	-244.12
Hebi	986.07	1002.98	1036.23	16.91	33.25	50.16
Zhumadian	8461.20	8790.47	8961.38	329.27	170.91	500.18
Xinxiang	4433.38	4416.41	4374.34	-16.97	-42.07	-59.04
Jiaozuo	1377.01	1474.78	1544.38	97.78	69.60	167.38
Zhengzhou	803.53	816.72	1033.38	13.18	216.67	229.85
Sanmenxia	157.99	155.68	215.80	-2.31	60.12	57.81
Kaifeng	2985.51	3094.39	2892.45	108.88	-201.94	-93.06
Nanyang	6585.83	6447.06	6433.59	-138.77	-13.47	-152.24
Luoyang	1126.54	973.74	1390.92	-152.80	417.17	264.38
Jiyuan	170.42	188.97	181.10	18.56	-7.88	10.68
Shangqiu	6773.05	6988.87	6753.22	215.82	-235.66	-19.84

Pingdingshan	2429.68	2400.74	2400.67	-28.94	-0.07	-29.00
Xinyang	1862.07	1820.99	2052.91	-41.09	231.92	190.83
Xuchang	2394.01	2311.04	2319.86	-82.97	8.82	-74.15
Luohe	1904.38	1937.27	1810.90	32.89	-126.37	-93.48
Total	56369.09	57211.98	56846.69	842.89	-365.30	477.60

From 2015 to 2019, wheat-growing areas in Henan Province exhibited a pattern of centralization, with a further concentration in the southeastern region. The planted area showed an upward trend, with particularly significant growth in traditional farming regions in eastern and southern Henan, such as Zhoukou, Zhumadian, and Shangqiu. The wheat cultivation areas in Zhoukou and Zhumadian increased by over 300 km², making them the core regions of the province's expansion [16], while some areas in Luoyang and Nanyang showed a declining trend.

Figure 5: Changes in Wheat Cultivation Patterns

Between 2019 and 2024, the spatial distribution of wheat cultivation areas in Henan Province underwent significant changes, characterized by a decline in the east, an increase in the west, stability in the south, and adjustments in the north. The changes were most pronounced in the eastern plains, where the wheat cultivation area in Zhoukou City decreased by 611.70 km²; the dark brown area shown in Figure 5c precisely reflects this negative growth. Furthermore, due to factors such as the conversion of farmland for urbanization and adjustments in crop structure, wheat cultivation areas in eastern Henan cities such as Kaifeng and Shangqiu have also shrunk. Meanwhile, cultivation areas in western and southern regions, including Luoyang, Zhengzhou, and Xinyang, have shown relatively significant growth, further revealing that the province's wheat cultivation center is undergoing a structural shift.

5. Conclusion

Between 2015 and 2024, the spatial pattern of wheat cultivation in the study area exhibited an evolutionary trend characterized by an initial concentration followed by dispersion of coverage, with slight fluctuations in the

dominant direction but a relatively stable morphological structure. This finding provides important quantitative evidence for understanding the dynamic response mechanisms of agricultural production space in this region.

The spatial distribution of wheat cultivation across the province is primarily governed by macro-topographic patterns and zonation factors related to water and heat conditions, resulting in a highly stable structural pattern. Latitudinal and longitudinal profile analyses reveal that, driven by both arable land protection policies and advancements in agricultural technology, wheat cultivation has concentrated in the core plain region, exhibiting an evolutionary trend characterized by “stable total area and strengthened core.”

Over the past decade, traditional core production areas have experienced a sharp decline in area, indicating that, amid rapid urbanization, grain production space is facing the expansion of construction land. This evolving pattern has not only reshaped the spatial allocation of agricultural resources within the province but also provides crucial scientific evidence for Henan Province to optimize the demarcation of permanent basic farmland and establish a differentiated ecological compensation mechanism for major grain-producing regions in the future.

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